

April 30, 2024

<https://ijoabs.com/>
[DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.)

Effectiveness of Agro Ecological Practices for Weed Management in Rice-Beans Cropping Systems

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Received Date: 16-Mar-2023

Accepted Date: 30-Apr-2023

Published Date: 30-Apr-2024

Abstract

Weed infestation is one of the major constraints in rice production within Makwale irrigation scheme. This study was carried out to assess the effectiveness of agro-ecological practices in managing weeds. A split split plot experiment was laid down under randomized complete block design. The main plot treatments were three residues management (removed, burned and incorporated), treatments in subplots were different crops varieties: beans were (Wanja, Uyole 96 and Mshindi) and rice was (Super Zambia, Faya and SARO 5). In sub sub plot treatments were four different weed management regimes; mechanical weeding twice (MW2), mechanical weeding + pre-emergence (PM), pre-emergence only (PO) and control (CO). The highest weed control efficiency was obtained from PM with lower weed count, height/length and weed biomass and the lowest was CO for all common weed species identified in both seasons $P < 0.001$. Treatments MW2 and PM revealed high efficiency in weed control resulted into high crop yield; in beans, the highest seed weight was 572 kg/ha in MW2 followed by 490g/ha in PM, and the lowest was 208.5 kg/ha in CO plot. In rice, the highest yield was 3502 kg/ha in MW2 followed by 2789 kg/ha in PM, and the lowest was 2398 kg/ha in CO at $P < 0.001$. Therefore, for better growth and higher yields (PM) is recommended to farmers in bean-rice rotation as has revealed well in control of *Oryza rufipogon* as a noxious weed in the study area which is difficult to control by other methods.

Keywords: Agro ecological practices, weed managements, cropping systems

1. INTRODUCTION

Weeds infestation are stated as a major problem in crop production as they do compete on resources with crops, increase production cost and cause crop loss up to 34 % (Oerke 2006& Rodenburg *et al.*, 2009). Some common agronomic factors that contribute to weed problems are mono-cropping, and delayed weed control interventions. Singh (2017 & Ellen *et al.*, 2014) reported that *Echinochloa crus-galli* and *Oryza rufipogon* are species considered one of the world's worst weeds and can reduce crop yields and cause forage crops to fail by removing up to 80% of the available soil nitrogen in rice fields. Currently agriculture experiences conflicting challenges due to the demand of aggregate production at the same time reducing environmental impacts caused by intensive use of synthetic agro-inputs (Albrecht *et al.*, 2016). In agroecology, agroecosystems can be manipulated to expand production efficiency sustainability, with fewer negative environmental impacts and lower use of external inputs (Gliessman, 2006). Agroecological weed management comprises environment-

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friendly techniques like crop rotation, mulching, cover crops and incorporation of crop residues that efficiently suppress weeds without causing negative effects to environment, contrasting to the harmful effects caused by herbicides (Blanco *et al.*, 2021). In agro ecology, weed management tools can be integrated to manage weeds in long-term while reducing herbicide dependence (Swanton *et al.*, 2008, Adeux *et al.*, 2017, Colbach & Cordeau 2018, Adeux *et al.*, 2019 & Yvoz *et al.*, 2020). Also depending on sufficient crop residues available, incorporation of crop residues might be one of the methods to control weeds in rice fields by affecting its emergence and growth (Mohler *et al.*, 2006, Jin *et al.*, 2021, Alonso *et al.*, 2081, Reberg *et al.*, 2011 & Yang *et al.*, 2018).

Also crop rotation been among the agroecological practices in weed management it reduces weed densities at crop emergence and inhibits long-term changes of weed populations towards species that are difficult to control. (Fakkar *et al.*, 2015). Field crops vary widely in their ability to compete with weeds and different crop varieties may also possess different competitive abilities depending on its capability to access resources such as light, water and nutrients (Mason *et al.*, 2006). Certain varieties have better capabilities to compete with weeds than others even though may perform differently in various regions and growing conditions (Blackshaw *et al.*, 2002 & Mason Spaner, 2006). Furthermore taller crop varieties are more competitive with weeds than shorter or semi-dwarf ones hence are much recommended to be used in combination with other agroecological packages (Watson *et al.*, 2006; Blackshaw *et al.*, 2002; Nazarko *et al.*, 2005; Mason & Spaner, 2006).

Mechanical weeding is environment-friendly but tiresome and highly labor demanding hence application of different pre-emergence herbicides was reported to be suitable for weed control (Mirza *et al.*, 2009 & Abdul *et al.*, 2013. The findings from Kaur & Singh (2015), Ahmed, 2005, Juraimi *et al.*, 2013; Vikas *et al.*, 2017) and Abhinandan *et al.* (2020) revealed that herbicides in combination with mechanical weeding were found quite effective in controlling noxious weeds and increasing crop yield. This work therefore aimed at assessing the combination of different agro ecological weed management practices in combating noxious weeds in rice fields.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Description of the study area and duration

The experiment was carried out at Makwale irrigation scheme in Kyela district located in the southern part of Mbeya region with latitude 9°37' south and longitude 33°52' east with annual rainfall ranging from 2000mm and 3000mm and mean daily temperature of 23°C.

Figure 1: Map of Tanzania Showing location of Makwale ward in Kyela district Council, Mbeya region

2.2 Treatments application in beans cycle

A split split plot experiment was laid down in randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications, each replication with three main plot, three subplots and four sub sub plots (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

Table 1. Treatments application in beans and rice seasons

Treatments during beans crop season		Sub sub plots (Size= 2 m x 2 m) (Weed management regimes)
Main Plot (Size =8 m x 11 m) (Rice Crop residues management)	Sub plot (Size =11 m x 2 m) (Beans crop varieties)	
1. Residues burned (RB)	1. Uyole 96 (U)	1. Mechanical weeding twice (MW2) done at 21 and 35 days after sowing
2. Residues removed (RR)	2. Wanja (W)	2. Pre emergence herbicide (Metolachlor 960EC) was sprayed on the 3 rd day from seed sowing by a rate of 1.5 L/ha + Mechanical weeding (PM) was done on 35 days after sowing by hand hoe.
3. Residues incorporated (RI)	3. Mshindi (M)	3. Pre emergence only (PO) (Metolachlor 960EC) was sprayed on the 3 rd day from seed sowing by a rate of 1.5 L/ha
		4. Control (CO) No weeding throughout the growing period
Treatments during rice crop season		
(Bean Crop residues management)	(Rice crop varieties)	
1. Residues burned (RB)	1. SARO 5 (S)	1. Mechanical weeding twice (MW2) done at 14 and 35 days from transplanting
2. Residues removed (RR)	2. Faya (F)	2. Pre emergence (Pretilachlor 500 g/l) was sprayed on the 3 rd day from transplanting by a rate of 1.5 L/ha + Mechanical weeding (PM) done at 42 days after transplanting by hand hoe.
3. Residues incorporated (RI)	3. Super Zambia (S.Z)	3. Pre emergence only (PO) (Pretilachlor 500 g/l) was sprayed on the 3 rd day from transplanting by a rate of 1.5 L/ha
		4. Control (CO) No weeding throughout the growing period

2.3 Data collection

Weeds data were collected four times from a quadrant of 1 m by 1 m placed systematical at the middle of 2 m x 2 m sub sub plot four times in each plot on the 7th day from emergence followed by interval of 7 days and at harvesting time (Vanhala, 2004).

2.3.1 Weed species count

Weed species were identified and counted using the guide handbook (Naidu, 2012) and application software called “Weed ID App for Android” developed by University of Missouri- Columbia. Weed counter was used in counting species identified.

2.3.2 Number of leaves per plant

Data on the number of leaves per plant was obtained by counting leaves of 10 weeds for each weed species found in each sub sub plot (Craig *et al.*, 2017).

2.3.3 Plant height/length cm plant⁻¹ of weeds per weed species

Data on plant height/length (cm) was obtained by measuring plant height from ground to the tip of plant where weeds growing horizontal the length were measured using 30cm rule. Ten plants were taken from each sub sub plot and their averages were recorded (Craig *et al.*, 2017).

2.3.4 Dry weight (Kg/ha)

Data on weed dry weight was collected at harvesting time 120 days from seed sowing or rice transplanting. All weeds within the quadrant were cut above the ground, cleaned using tape water and kept under shade condition for 24 hrs to eliminate excess moisture. There after the weeds were counted as per specie, dried in an oven at 70 °C for 72 hrs, weighed using a digital weighing balance, and dry weight (g) of the weed was measured and recorded (ICARDA, 2013).

2.3.5 Height of bean plant in (cm)

Data on the height of the plant (cm) were obtained by measuring plant height from the ground to the tip of the plant using a rule of 30cm length and their averages were recorded.

2.3.6 Number of bean seeds per pod

The selected beans plants were harvested by uprooting and seeds for each pod were counted and averages were recorded.

2.3.7 Weight of bean fresh pods (Kg/ha)

The harvested pods from demarcated plants were picked up and weighed using a digital weighing balance, and the weight was recorded.

2.3.8 Weight of bean dry seeds (Kg/ha)

Pods weighed for fresh weight were dried in the sunshine until they attained the average of 10-15% moisture content, weighed using a digital weighing balance and the weight was recorded.

2.3.9 Number of panicles per rice plant

At harvesting time, panicles were counted from 36 hills in each tiller plant, and their averages were recorded.

2.3.10 Number of rice grains per spikelet

Data of grains per spikelet were obtained by counting grains in each spikelet within the panicle for each rice tiller in 36 hills.

2.3.11 Grain weight (Kg/ha)

Data of grain weight were obtained by drying the harvested rice at the center grains from tillers in 36 hills, threshed, dried up to 10-15 % moisture content level, cleaned, weighed using the digital weighing balance in grams, converted into kilograms per hectare (kg/ha) and the weight was recorded as per protocol stated by IIRRI (1978).

2.4 Statistical analyses

Before analysis of variance (ANOVA), the collected data were organized using the excel sheet to facilitate the computation of spatial and temporal distribution indices as described by Arbab (2016). Then data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) at ($P \leq 0.05$) using GenStat 16th Edition statistical package. Treatment means were separated using Turkey's, significant.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Dominant weed species

Results for populations of dominant weed species across different weed management regimes deployed under this study are presented in Fig 2. However predominant weed species identified in the study area were *Cyperus spp.*, *Commelina spp.*, and *Oryza rufipogon*. *Cyperus spp.* such as *Cyperus esculentus* and *Cyperus rotundus* as perennial grass weeds with dual reproductive modes: through seeds and vegetative through underground rhizomes, bestowing difficulties in its control (Booth *et al.*, 2018). The weed management regimes showed highly significant differences in weed population within pre dominant weed species at $P < 0.001$. In beans season the highest weed population of *Cyperus spp.*, *Oryza rufipogon*, and *Commelina spp* (24.12, 95.76, 3.491) plants/1m² were recorded from control (CO) followed by the mechanical weeding twice (12.77, 36.34 and 2.852) plant/1m². In contrast, the lowest weed population was (5.06, 23.57 and 1.12) plant/1m² was recorded from the integration of Metolachlor 960g/l with mechanical weeding respectively at $P < 0.001$.

In rice season, the highest weed population of *Cyperus spp.*, *Oryza rufipogon*, and *Commelina* (61.12, 7.093 and 4.102 respectively) plant/ 1m² and the lowest weed population was (15.65, 1.167 and 2.417) plant/ 1m² respectively recorded from Pretilachlor 500 g/l) combined with mechanical weeding once at $P < 0.001$. Generally, all weeding regimes significantly reduced weed populations of almost all species considered in either bean or rice growing season. Combined application of pre-emergence herbicide and mechanical weeding (PM) reduced weed populations of *Cyperus spp.*, *Commelina spp.*, and *Oryza rufipogon*, to numbers that are significantly lower than the rest of the weed management regimes evaluated. It was also observed that, the effectiveness of the weed management regime on reducing weed population was hooked on weed specie being evaluated. For instance, compared to mechanical weeding twice, pre-emergence herbicide application significantly reduced populations of *Oryza rufipogon* and *Commelina spp* but not *Cyperus spp.*

A comparison of two growing seasons within rotations showed that the population of *Cyperus spp.*, and *Commelina spp.*, were higher during the rice growing season (second season), whereas *Oryza rufipogon* population was higher during bean growing season (first season). However, the effectiveness of each weed management regime was dependent on the weed specie being evaluated at the moment. For instance, during the common bean cycle, the solely applied pre-emergence herbicide: Metolachlor (960 g/L) at the rate of 1.5 L/ha was not very effective in reducing the population of *Cyperus spp.*, unlike *Oryza rufipogon* and *Commelina spp.*

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Mean values with the same letter(s) are not significantly different at P=0.001 according to Tukey’s (HSD) test.

Key: MW2: Mechanical weeding twice; PO: Pre-emergence only; CO: No weeding (Control); PM: Pre emergence herbicide and mechanical weeding;

Figure 2. Population of different weed species across varying weed management regimes within bean-rice rotation system at (P< 0.001) in Makwale irrigation scheme- Kyela district

3.3 Weed Heights/lengths (cm)

Results for the average heights of *Cyperus spp.* and *Oryza rufipogon*, and average lengths of *Commelina spp* were significantly influenced by different weed management options within the bean-rice cropping system as shown in Table 2. (P< 0.001). In beans season, the tallest weed plant height (9.833cm, 25.31 cm and 14.759 cm) was observed in control plots, and the shortest plant height (2.509 cm, 9.86 cm and 3.065 cm) was observed in PM plots for *Cyprus spp*, *Oryza rufipogon*, *Commelina spp* respectively. Generally, a combination of pre-emergence herbicide and mechanical weeding (PM) lowered the weed heights more effectively compared to either method deployed solely in both beans and rice growing seasons of the rotation at P< 0.001.

In the rice growing season, the heights of *Oryza rufipogon* were not statistically different for all weed management regimes except control treatment. The trends in heights of *Cyperus spp* across weed management regimes were similar to that in the first season: combined application of pre-emergence herbicide and mechanical weeding (PM) or mechanical weeding alone (MW2) reducing heights more significantly than either pre-emergence herbicide alone or control (CO) at P< 0.001. Consistent with the observation during the bean growing season, the plant lengths of *Commelina spp.* were statistically comparable for all weed management regimes, unlike the control plots.

Table 2. Heights/length of weed species

Weeding Regimes	Bean Growing Season			Rice Growing Season		
	<i>Cyperus spp.</i> (cm)	<i>Oryza rufipogon.</i> (cm)	<i>Commelina spp.</i> (cm)	<i>Cyperus spp.</i> (cm)	<i>Oryza rufipogon.</i> (cm)	<i>Commelina spp.</i> (cm)

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Pre emergence + mechanical	2.509a	9.86a	3.065a	5.101a	6.09a	2.03 a
Mechanical weeding twice	3.093a	9.83a	5.352ab	4.438a	9.8a	4.32 a
Pre emergence only	6.667b	16.77b	7.407b	7.528b	10.4a	6.04 a
Control	9.833c	25.31c	14.759c	7.074b	16.49b	11.759 b
PV	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.032	<0.001	<.001
CV	6.6	6.4	13.6	15.6	13.8	13.6
LSD	1.476	2.948	2.438	2.421	3.885	4.508

Mean values with the same letter(s) are not significantly different at P=0.001 according to Tukey's (HSD) test

Key; MW2: Mechanical weeding twice; PO: Pre emergence only; CO: No weeding (Control); PM: Pre emergence herbicide and mechanical weeding; CV: Coefficient of Variation; PV: Probability Value; LSD: Least Significant Differences of means (5% level).

3.4 Number of weed leaves per plant

The results in Table 3 displays very high significant different in average number of leaves per weed plant assessed across different weed management regimes within the bean-rice cropping system. In beans season, the highest number of leaves (5.639, 4.704 and 9.889) for *Cyperus spp.*, *Oryza* and *rufipogon Commelina spp.*, respectively were recorded in the control plot, while the lowest number (1.787, 3.083 and 2.056) *Cyperus spp.*, *Oryza* and *rufipogon Commelina spp* respectively were recorded in a combined pre-emergence and mechanical weeding once. In rice season, the highest number of weed leaves (2.38, 4.278 and 8.213) of *Cyperus spp.*, *Oryza* and *rufipogon Commelina spp.*, respectively, while the lowest (2.315, 1.843 and 4.278) in pre-emergence combined with mechanical weeding once for *Cyperus spp.*, *Oryza* and *rufipogon Commelina spp* respectively at $P < 0.001$.

Across the two growing seasons, combined application of pre-emergence herbicide and mechanical weeding once was observed to effectively stand out in reducing number of weed leaves significantly for almost all species evaluated under this study. Except for *Cyperus spp.*, in the rice growing season, significantly highest numbers of *Oryza rufipogon*, and *Commelina spp.*, were recorded under control plots.

Table 3. Number of weed Leaves

Weeding regimes	Number of Weed Leaves in Beans			Number of Weed Leaves in Rice		
	<i>Cyperus spp.</i>	<i>Oryza rufipogon</i>	<i>Commelina spp.</i>	<i>Cyperus spp.</i>	<i>Oryza rufipogon</i>	<i>Commelina spp.</i>
Pre emergence + mechanical	1.787a	3.083a	2.056a	2.315 a	1.843a	4.278 a
Mechanical weeding twice	2.361a	2.741a	5.204b	2.361 a	3.083b	4.676 a
Pre emergence only	4.528b	3.833b	4.759b	2.361 a	3.296bc	6.657 ab
Control	5.639c	4.704c	9.889c	2.38 a	4.278c	8.213 b
PV	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.992	<0.001	0.002
CV	2.3	6.7	19.8	5.5	32.1	29.1
LSD	0.74	0.3902	1.614	0.4256	0.884	2.191

Mean values with the same letter(s) are not significantly different at P=0.001 according to Tukey's (HSD) test

Key: MW2: Mechanical weeding twice; PO: Pre-emergence only; CO: No weeding (Control); PM: Pre emergence herbicide and mechanical weeding; CV: Coefficient of Variation; PV: Probability Value; LSD: Least Significant Differences of means (5 % level).

3.5 Weed dry matter (biomass) (Kg/ha)

The average dry matter weights of three weed species as noxious and pre dominant: *Cyperus spp.*, *Oryza rufipogon*, and *Commelina spp.*, under different weed management regimes in bean-rice rotation, are shown in Table 4. A significant difference in weed dry matter was observed among weed management practices regimes ($P < 0.001$). The lowest weed dry matter weight in bean season was (39.7 kg/ha) for *Cyperus spp* recorded after application of Metolachlor (960 g/L) at the rate of 1.5 L/ha, plus Mechanical weeding 35 days after seed emergence and the highest was (1083.3 kg/ha) of *Oryza rufipogon* recorded in control plot at $P < 0.001$. In rice season, the lowest dry matter weight for *Cyperus spp.* (41.7 kg/ha) recorded from Pretilachlor 500g/l) at the rate of 1.5 L/ha and the highest was *Commelina spp* (621.3 kg/ha) in a control plot at $P < 0.001$. During the bean growing season, all weed management regimes lead to significant decrement in average dry weights of *Cyperus spp.*, *Oryza rufipogon*, and *Commelina spp.*, compared to control plots.

Table 4. Weeds Dry matter (biomass)

Weeding regimes	Weed Dry Matter (kg/ha) in Bean			Weed Dry Matter (kg/ha) in Rice		
	<i>Cyperus spp.</i>	<i>Oryza rufipogon</i>	<i>Commelina spp.</i>	<i>Cyperus spp.</i>	<i>Oryza rufipogon</i>	<i>Commelina spp.</i>
Pre emergence + mechanical	39.7a	77.3a	10a	41.7 ab	86.7a	205.3a
Mechanical weeding twice	71.8a	126.6a	85.8ab	30.7 a	130a	220.2a
Pre emergence only	144.7b	313.9b	124.1b	42.5 ab	306.3b	589.8b
Control	193.6c	1083.3c	305.4c	55.9 b	513.5c	621.3b
PV	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.008	<0.001	<0.001
CV	10.9	13	23	28.5	39.5	59.7
LSD	31.5	115.92	69	14.096	131.6219	203.22

Mean values with the same letter(s) are not significantly different at $P=0.001$ according to Tukey's (HSD) test

Key: MW2: Mechanical weeding twice; PO: Pre emergence only; CO: No weeding (Control); PM: Pre emergence herbicide and mechanical weeding; CV: Coefficient of Variation; PV: Probability Value; LSD: Least Significant Differences of means (5 % level).

3.6 Crop growth and yield (Kg/ha)

The findings (Fig 3 and 4) revealed very high significant difference in bean height, number of seed per pod, fresh pod weight, dry pod weight and grain weight of beans were observed between weed management regimes evaluated at ($P < 0.001$) Fig.3 and Fig.4 The highest number of all growth and yield components was obtained from the mechanical weeding twice plots, followed by mechanical weeding combined with (Metolachlor (960 g/L) at the rate of 1.5 L/ha and the lowest was recorded on a control plot.

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Mean values with the same letter(s) are not significantly different at $P=0.001$ according to Tukey's (HSD) test

Key: CO =Un-weeded plots, MW2 = Mechanical weeding twice, PO=Pre emergence only PM =Pre emergence and Mechanical weeding

Figure 3. Results of the effect of weed management regimes on the height of bean plant and number of bean seeds per pod at ($P < 0.001$) in Makwale Irrigation scheme- Kyela district

Mean values with the same letter(s) are not significantly different at $P=0.001$ according to Tukey's (HSD) test

Key: CO =Un-weeded plots, MW2 = Mechanical weeding twice, PO=Pre emergence only PM =Pre emergence and Mechanical weeding

Figure 4. The effect of weed management regimes on yield parameters at ($P < 0.001$) in Makwale Irrigation scheme- Kyela district

In rice season analysis of variance revealed very highly significances difference ($P < 0.001$) in the number of panicles per tiller, number of grain spikelets and weight of grains (Fig. 5). The differences were influenced by

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the four different weeding regimes where their highest numbers were recorded in mechanical weeding twice and pre-emergence herbicide (Pretilachlor 500 g/l) at the rate of 1.5 L/ha) combined with mechanical weeding once, the lowest in control plots for the yield and growth parameters showed significant differences.

Mean values with the same letter(s) are not significantly different at $P=0.001$ according to Tukey's (HSD) test

Key: CO =Un-weeded plots, MW2 = mechanical Weeding twice, PO=Pre emergence only PM =Pre emergence and Mechanical weeding

Figure 5. The effect of weed management regimes on rice yield parameters (Number of panicles per tiller, number of grain spikelets and Weight of grains (Kg/ha) in rice) at ($P < 0.001$) in Makwale Irrigation scheme- Kyela district

4. DISCUSSION

The higher reduction rate in population of *Oryza rufipogon* was observed in the second season across weed management practices but mainly in Pre emergence herbiced combined with mechanical weeding and Mechanical weeding twice. This might be due to the reduced number of germinated weed seeds and reduced newly produced weed seeds deposited in the soil during beans season. *Oryza rufipogon* is a perennial wild relative of cultivated rice hardly distinguishable from cultivated rice (Hartzler & Buhler, 2007). Due to its vegetative mimicry, *Oryza rufipogon* is considered among the important weeds in rice fields (Rodenburg *et al.*, 2011). *Commelina spp.* is a perennial herb that propagates itself primarily through sexual reproduction by seeds and asexual reproduction by stem cuttings and rooting (Isaac *et al.*, 2013). These findings in the current study are in agreement with that of Amare *et al.* (2016), who reported that the highest weed count was identified in weeded plot, and the lowest weed count was from the integration of pre-emergence herbicide (S-metolachlor) combined with mechanical weeding twice.

Populations of weed species assessed varied between the two seasons. These variations were attributed to disparities in weed management practices of the two crops. This observation was recurring in almost all treatments, including control. The findings showed that minimal use of pre-emergence herbicides in combination with mechanical weeding effectively controlled *Cyperus spp.*, *Commelina spp.*, and *Oryza rufipogon*, which were the dominant weed species in the area. This might be due to the fact that, pre-emergence herbicides (Metolachlor and Pretilachlor) control early germinating weed and growth by inhibiting cell division through interfering biosynthesis of fatty acids, which are vital for plant growth and maintenance while

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mechanical weeding reduces recently emerging weeds during the crop growth cycle. These results are supported by the findings by Amare *et al.* (2016) & Singh *et al.* (2013), who reported that the best weed control regime was a combination of pre-emergence herbicides and mechanical weeding. Significant decrease in weed population or weed count from season one to season two with beans – rice rotation might be due to an unsteady and unreceptive environment that inhibits the propagation of a particular weed species. This current finding also agrees with the work done by Fakkar *et al.* (2015), who reported a significant effect on number of weeds per area in crop sequence where a larger number of weeds were recorded in the first season compared to the second of crop rotation.

The reduction of weed height and length in PM is likely contributed by the effect of Metolachlor 960 g/L, which constrains weed seedling shoots growth once applied pre weed seed germination, while mechanical weeding involves removing the succeeded growing weeds. In these plots, only younger emerging weeds existed throughout the growing season. The same findings were reported by Xile *et al.* (2020) that the significant effects of Metolachlor 960 g/L to weeds is reducing root length and growth. During the first season of the rotation (bean growing season), combined application of pre-emergence herbicide and mechanical weeding (PM) or mechanical weeding alone (MW2) resulted in significantly shorter weed plant heights for *Cyperus spp.*, and *Oryza rufipogon*, followed by pre-emergence herbicide alone and then control plots (CO). In the rice growing season, weed heights of *Oryza rufipogon* were not statistically different for all weed management regimes with exception of control. The trends in heights of *Cyperus spp* across weed management regimes were similar to that in the first season: combined application of pre-emergence herbicide and mechanical weeding (PM) or mechanical weeding alone (MW2) reducing heights more significantly than either pre-emergence herbicide alone or control (CO). Consistent with the observation during the bean growing season, the plant lengths of *Commelina spp.* were statistically comparable for all weed management regimes, unlike the control plots.

Despite that, all weed management regimes reduced weed leave numbers significantly compared to control, mechanical weeding twice (MW2) had weeds with lesser leave numbers compared to plots with pre-emergence herbicide alone during the bean growing season. The same results were reported by Malete *et al.* (2014) that mechanical weeding twice significantly reduced weed growth and dry matter compared to un weeded plots which sustained higher weed growth. However, during the rice growing season, the number of leaves of *Cyperus spp.* was not significantly influenced by the weed management regime applied. For *Oryza rufipogon* and *Commelina spp.*, a comparison between either applying pre-emergence herbicide alone or mechanical weeding alone revealed no significant differences in reducing weed leave numbers.

Lowest weed biomass for all three pre-dominant weed species in both beans and rice cycle in PM might be due to the aggregate effect of herbicide and mechanical weeding. This observation may mean less competition between the crop and weeds as pre-emergence herbicide combined with mechanical weeding thrived in eradicating most of the subsequently weeds. This resulted to reduced competition between the crop and weeds for the basic plant growth resources compared to CO plot, which had greater ability in competition on crop space, light, water and carbon dioxide, the weed suppressed plant growth and became dominant over the crops. The results of the competition was a higher weed population, higher weed biomass in control plots and lower weed population in PM and MW2 plots, ultimately with lower weed biomass. This finding is supported by the work of Dadari (2003) that competition of weeds toward crop commences at the germination of the crop and goes all over to the senescence period interfering with both growth and yield parameters adversely. It was also observed that, for any weed specie evaluated during this first season, deploying either mechanical weeding alone (MW2) or in combination with pre-emergence herbicides (PM) results into the highest weed dry weights in rice growing season.

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Low dry weight in PM and MW2 might be due to the ability of pre-emergence herbicide to reduce the number of weed seeds to germinate, reduced the growth rate for the germinated one and finally made it easy to remove mechanically. These results are in agreement with Singh and Sekhon (2013) & Amare *et al.* (2016), who found that, the removal of newly emerged weed species mechanically contributed to the low weed dry matter. Moreover, the highest weed dry matter was in control and finally weeds dry matter decreased when herbicides are combined with mechanical weeding and became effective weed control. Also, Kumar *et al.* (1997) & Rana *et al.* (2002) observed a decrease in weed biomass when herbicide application combined with mechanical weeding in common beans.

During rice season, application of herbicide alone led to a significant reduction of dry weights of only one weed species: *Oryza rufipogon*, while the dry weights of *Cyperus spp.* and *Commelina spp.* were statistically comparable to control plots. Similar findings were reported by Gurgbal & Sekhon *et al.* (2013) that biomass and weed growth parameters were higher in the plot treated with herbicide as the herbicide didn't control the predominance of *Commelina benghalensis*. Also, this is likely to be contributed by kind of propagated materials such as; *Oryza rufipogon* is propagated by seed only which deposited in the soil from the previous season while *Cyperus spp.* and *Commelina spp.* are propagated by vegetative parts which are not controlled by pre-emergence herbicide ultimately gave a greater chance of surviving in the field and finally having higher biomass. These findings are in agreement with the work by Paulo *et al.* (2019), who stipulated that rapid control of *Commelina benghalensis* was obtained from application of post-emergence herbicide (Saflufencil and Flumioxazin) rather than pre-emergence herbicides (Indaziflam).

High growth and yield obtained in mechanical weeding twice was due to double advantage of soil manipulation and enhancing crop growth and yield with reduced weed population for competition. Also, herbicides mode of action and time of application of (Metolachlor (960g/L) applied on to a well-prepared soil-controlled weeds effectively by inhibiting weed emergence when applied at pre-emergence of the crop and weeds finally reduced weeds emerged which might easily compete with crop cause significant yield reduction. The higher performance of beans in growth and yield in Mw2 and PM might also be contributed by the effectiveness of weed control of these two regimes as indicated in Fig.2 of weed population, Fig.3, Fig.4 of growth parameters and Fig.5 of dry matter weight. Also, this might be because pre-emergence prevented weeds not to germinate and early to weed mechanically resulted in early weed removal, enabling plants to have more resources for growth. These results agree with (Kiss *et al.*, 2017 and Bedry *et al.*, 2007) and found that twice hand weeding significantly increased shoot length while unweeded treatment had decreased plant height. The same results also were reported by Ahmed *et al.* (2011) that mechanical weeding twice in beans had the highest plant growth and yield components as there was less competition for growth resources due to efficient weed control.

Preeminence herbicide combined with mechanical weeding once, despite having high weed control efficiency relieved less growth and yield compared to MW2. This might be due to chemical injury, as visual observations during plant growth in the field showed that Metolachlor (1.5 L/ha) was toxic to the common bean and caused injury to the emerging beans' shoot and leaves, resulting in stunting during the early stages of growth. Nevertheless, the symptoms disappeared, and the crop completely recovered after two weeks after planting. These results closely match the findings of Babiker *et al.* (2014), who reported toxicity caused by oxyfluorfen and pendimethalin to common beans at the early stages of growth.

High growth and yield components in mechanical weeding twice (MW2) might be attributed to its efficiency in weed control that profuse weeds didn't completely removed from the first weeding were finished in the second weeding, while twice soil manipulation improves aeration and water circulation hence boosted rapid growth and yield. The highest weed control was observed in pre-emergence integrated with mechanical weeding once (PM) though it resulted in a low yield in comparison with MW2. This might be due to the fact that soils were

disturbed once in (PM) throughout the growing season compared to PM, PO and CO plots which soils were not disturbed at all resulting to lowest growth and yield. This justifies the vital of soil manipulation during weed control. Though mechanical weeding twice would require additional expenditure for hired labor, alternative methods like integration of pre-emergence herbicide and mechanical weeding once also revealed increased growth and yield. The previous report by Kristine *et al.* (2020) that the application of pre-emergence herbicide produced a higher yield than control in rice but less compared to hand weeding twice.

Low yield and growth components in control or un-weeded plots were due to the fact that the high weed density in CO plot (Fig 5) justifies the severe infestation of weeds which suppressed plant growth and yield as well as increased tiller mortality, decreased shoot and grain production at large. These results are in line with the research findings by (Javier *et al.*, 2005; Joshi *et al.*, 2013; Chauhan *et al.* 2015; Antralina *et al.*, 2015) who reported significant yield reduction associated with un-weeded plots (CO) on the justification of weed competition for basic resources for growth and yielded with the rice plant.

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Increase use of post emergence (glyphosate) herbicide in the study area for control of noxious weed (*Oryza rufipogon*) was influenced by the method used by farmers to control the weed after crop harvest while the weed seeds were already deposited in the soil and increasing weed seed bank. However, a single method of weed control does not offer adequate long-term weed management instead results in increasing resistance. Thus, integration of different weed control methods is critical to weed control and can be a valuable contribution to improved crop yield. Among the weed management regime practices evaluated low application rates (1.5l/ha) of pre emergence herbicides used in beans and rice cycles combined with mechanical weeding once did offer efficient weed control options that could shift concentration from industrial agrochemicals to agroecological practices for the management of weeds particular the noxious *Oryza rufipogon*. The study recommends that, rice cultivation with inclusion of legumes (beans) during off season and weed control through mechanical weeding combined with minimal amount of pre-emergence herbicide (1l/ha) will results to total reduction of *Oryza rufipogon* in the study area.

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